

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION ON THE COMPLEX FORMATION BETWEEN PYROPHOSPHATE ION AND BERYLLIUM ION IN SOLUTION

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The complex formation between pyrophosphate ion and beryllium ion has been studied in solution by different physico-chemical methods such as transport, thermometric, conductometric, p_n -measurements and cryoscopy in saturated sodium sulphate solutions. It has been proved conclusively that in solution containing excess of alkali pyrophosphate and beryllium salt, anionic complex ions having beryllium in the anion are present. The complex ions are of the type $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-3}$ and $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-6}$ and are found to exist in simple monomeric form. In presence of excess of pyrophosphate ion, the complex formation may be represented in a stepwise manner as follows :

The early attempt to prepare sodium beryllium pyrophosphate was made by Persoz (*Annales*, 1848, 64, 174). Atterberg (*Svenska Akad. Handb.*, 1873, 12, 34) observed the solubility of beryllium pyrophosphate in sodium pyrophosphate solution and found that two molecules of sodium pyrophosphate can take up more than one molecule of beryllium pyrophosphate. The solution of beryllium pyrophosphate in excess of sodium pyrophosphate does not give the test of beryllium ion. When the solution is, however, boiled with nitric acid, the presence of beryllium ion is indicated by ammonia, ammonium sulphide and sodium carbonate. It shows that in excess of sodium pyrophosphate solution beryllium ion forms complex ion or ions with pyrophosphate ion. But no definite evidence has been put forward upto now in its favour. Even the literature on sodium beryllium pyrophosphate does not record any physico-chemical investigation on the nature of beryllium complexes present in excess of pyrophosphate solution.

The reaction between pyrophosphate ion and beryllium ion has been studied from the standpoint of physico-chemical properties of the mixed solutions by methods such as transport, thermometric, conductometric, p_n -measurements and cryoscopy in saturated sodium sulphate solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Transport Measurements

The apparatus used is due to Duval (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1938, v, 5, 1020). It consists of a U-shaped glass tube of 12 cm. in height and 6 mm. (internal diameter) bore. The two branches of the glass tube are provided with two stop-cocks. The stop-cocks are fitted without any grease and do not allow normal diffusion. A third branch is attached at the centre of the base of the glass tube. The experimental liquid can be introduced in the curved portion of the glass tube without opening the stop-

cocks through this branch. It also makes the apparatus stable. The branches above the stop-cocks contain an indifferent electrolyte. They are then connected through a commutator to 105 volts (D.C.). The current is passed for 10 minutes to 4 hours as the case may be. The electrolyte in the branches above the stop-cocks were analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively after the passage of the electric current. The process was repeated by changing the direction of the current. Experiments with colloidal particles should not be made with this apparatus because the colloidal particles choke the capillary passage of the stop-cocks. The current should not be passed for such a long period of time as to allow the diffusing ions under electric current to reach the electrode surface. In that case secondary reaction will take place at the electrode surfaces and the true result may not be obtained. The stop-cocks are freshly grinded usually after use for three to four months. Otherwise diffusion, when no current is passing, will take place. In order to see whether diffusion takes place or not, when stop-cocks are closed and no current is passing, distilled water is kept in the portion below the stop-cocks and hydrochloric acid is taken in the branches above the stop-cocks. After 24 hours, the distilled water is taken out through the third branch and is tested for chloride.

The solution containing excess of sodium pyrophosphate and beryllium sulphate is placed in the glass tube below the stop-cocks through the third branch. The stop-cocks are kept closed. A very dilute solution of sodium chloride is taken in the two branches above the stop-cocks. Electric current is passed for 30 minutes. The solution of the anode branch is taken out and heated with a few drops of nitric acid. It is then evaporated to dryness. The residue is taken with water and tested for beryllium with quinalizarine. Beryllium was found in the anode. The direction of the current was reversed and again beryllium was found in the anodic liquid. A blank test with the dilute solution of sodium chloride used was also performed and beryllium was found to be absent. It proves without any ambiguity that in solutions containing excess of sodium pyrophosphate and beryllium sulphate, beryllium ion is present as anionic complex ion.

Thermometric Measurements

The thermometric apparatus is the same as that already described by the author (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 57) in a previous paper.

The reagents used were of A.R. quality. Standard solution of sodium pyrophosphate was prepared by direct weighing in a chemical balance. The strength of sodium pyrophosphate solution was, however, checked by converting the pyrophosphate into phosphate and then estimating the total phosphate as magnesium pyrophosphate. Potassium pyrophosphate used was prepared from anhydrous dipotassium hydrogen phosphate by the method of Kolthoff and Walters (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 8). Standard solutions of potassium pyrophosphate was prepared by estimating the total phosphate of the solution as already stated. Beryllium was estimated as beryllium oxide (BeO).

The thermometric titration results are shown graphically in Figures 1 to 3 and are discussed below.

FIG. 1

Vol. of 0.2216 M Be sulphate soln. added.

Upper curve refers to 40 c.c. of 0.1 M-Na pyrophosphate soln. and the lower one to 40 c.c. of water.

The thermometric titration curves of alkali pyrophosphate with beryllium sulphate and *vice versa* give two breaks corresponding to the complex ions of the type $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-2}$ and $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-2}$, taking the simplest values of the ratios. The break due to the formation of normal beryllium pyrophosphate is shown in Fig. 3. The second break in Fig. 1 may also be explained as due to the formation of complex sulphates according to the following equation:

(Literature on double sulphates of beryllium and sodium show that compound of the above formula does exist). Now if the point pyro : beryllium = 1 : 1 be due to the complex ion $[\text{Be}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^{-2}$ and not due to $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-2}$, then the titration curve of beryllium sulphate with potassium pyrophosphate would have been different. For, in this case beryllium pyrophosphate is precipitated first and the corresponding amount of potassium sulphate is produced. Now in the solution there is not enough beryllium sulphate present to react with potassium sulphate to form the complex ion $[\text{Be}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^{-2}$ and so the break at the point pyro : beryllium = 1 : 1 would not appear. But experimentally it is found otherwise. If, however, both the complex ions $[\text{Be}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^{-2}$ and $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-2}$ are formed simultaneously, then the second break in Fig. 1 would have been shifted to the higher value of beryllium sulphate concentration. Since no such shift is observed, it may be concluded that the stability of the complex ion $[\text{Be}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^{-2}$ (provided it exists) must be very much less than that of the ion $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-2}$, so that at the point pyro : beryllium = 1 : 1, the complex ion $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-2}$ predominates and the reaction between pyrophosphate ion and beryllium ion may be considered to be the main reaction. The third break in Fig. 3 is

FIG. 2

Upper curve refers to 40 c.c. of 0.2 M-Na-pyrophosphate soln. and lower one to 40 c.c. of water.

FIG. 3

The curve refers to 40 c.c. of 0.2216 M Be sulphate soln.

probably due to the mixture of two compounds $K_2[Be(P_2O_7)]$ and $K_6[Be(P_2O_7)_2]$ and does not correspond to any definite compound formation. For no such break appears in the titration curve of sodium pyrophosphate with beryllium sulphate solution.

Conductivity Measurements

The conductivity apparatus consists of a box type conductivity bridge of Leeds and Northrup Co., Philadelphia, U.S.A. An audio-frequency oscillator is used as a sound source and a visual indicator served for the detection of the null point.

The conductivity titrations of alkali-pyrophosphates were made with beryllium nitrate solution and are shown in Fig. 4. The conductance-composition curves were drawn from measurements with sodium pyrophosphate and beryllium sulphate solutions.

The conductometric titration curves support the thermometric results already stated. The conductance of the alkali pyrophosphate solutions decreases with the addition of beryllium nitrate solution up to the point pyro : beryllium = 2 : 1. After this point the slope of the curve changes sharply indicating the formation of the complex ion $[Be(P_2O_7)_2]^{-6}$. The total reaction in solution may be represented as

when R = Na or K.

But from the above equation, the fall in conductance of alkali pyrophosphate solutions with addition of beryllium nitrate solution up to the point pyro : metal = 2 : 1 cannot be explained. Due to the formation of the complex ion $[Be(P_2O_7)_2]^{-6}$, eleven ions are produced for every ten ions present in the solution. It can, however, be accounted for by supposing that the formation of the complex ion $[Be(P_2O_7)_2]^{-6}$ is attended with suppression of hydrolysis of alkali pyrophosphate solution. This is expected

FIG. 4

to be so. For in alkali pyrophosphate solution an equilibrium of the type

exists. If, however, free pyrophosphate ion is removed from the system, as in the complex formation between beryllium ion and the pyrophosphate ion, the equilibrium relation of (3) is shifted towards the left. That is, the concentration of free hydroxyl ion, an ion with very high ionic mobility compared to the other ions present, decreases in the solution. The net effect is observed in the lowering of the conductance of the alkali pyrophosphate solutions with the addition of beryllium nitrate solution, although total number of ions increases in the solution. This process continues up to the point pyro : beryllium = 2 : 1. The conductance of the alkali pyrophosphate solutions increases sharply after the point pyro : beryllium = 2 : 1. This is due to the for-

mation of the complex ion $(\text{BeP}_2\text{O}_7)^{-2}$ in increasing concentration. Because, with its formation ten ions are produced for every seven ions present in the solution, and hence increase in the conductance is observed. The rate of change of conductance takes place linearly up to the point pyro : beryllium = 1 : 1. At this point the rate of increase in the conductance decreases. It may be explained as follows: After the point pyro : beryllium = 1 : 1, beryllium pyrophosphate is produced according to the following equation :

In the present case four ions are produced for every three ions present in the solution and so the conductance of the solution increases. But the rate of change of conductance, after the point pyro : beryllium = 1 : 1 is, however, less than that before it.

For equimolecular solutions, the conductance-composition curves (Fig. 5) of sodium pyrophosphate and beryllium sulphate solutions show maxima at the point pyro : beryllium = 2 : 1. The maxima is found to be independent of the concentrations of the reactants used and therefore gives true composition of the compound formed. Hence

FIG. 5

Upper curve refers to Be sulphate = 0.09533 M and Na pyrophosphate soln. = 0.0533 M.
 Lower curve refers to Be sulphate = 0.02 M and pyrophosphate = 0.02 M.

the complex ion is $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-6}$. The reaction between pyrophosphate ion and beryllium ion may thus be supposed to take place as follows :

p_H Measurements

The p_{H} measurements were made with a Beckmann p_{H} -meter model G of National Technical Laboratories, South Pasadena, California. Solutions containing the same amount of sodium pyrophosphate and different amounts of beryllium nitrate solutions were prepared. The p_{H} of these solutions were then measured with Beckmann p_{H} -meter. The corrections in the p_{H} values due to the presence of a large excess of sodium ions in the solutions were made with the help of a chart supplied with the instrument. The corrected p_{H} were then plotted against the concentrations of beryllium nitrate used and the graph (Fig. 6) obtained.

FIG. 6

The p_{H} -titration curve indicates a sharp fall in p_{H} at the point corresponding to the formation of the complex ion $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-6}$. This supports the explanation already given for the initial fall in the conductivity titration curves. The change in p_{H} at the point pyrophosphate: beryllium = 1: 1 is not very marked. This, however, depends upon the relative stabilities of the complex ions $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-2}$ and $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-6}$. After the point representing normal beryllium pyrophosphate, the p_{H} of the solution changes slowly with the addition of beryllium nitrate solution.

Cryoscopy Measurements in Saturated Sodium Sulphate Solution

From the preceding investigations it has been definitely proved that in a solution containing excess of sodium pyrophosphate and beryllium salt, two complex ions, in which the ratios of pyro : beryllium are 2 : 1 and 1 : 1, exist. It has been tacitly assumed that the above complex ions exist in simple monomeric form in solution. But no direct evidence has been cited in its favour. The cryoscopy in saturated sodium sulphate solution is expected to throw some light on this matter.

Cryoscopy in saturated sodium sulphate solution is due to Darmois (*Bull. soc. chim. Belg.* 1927, 36, 64). The apparatus consists of a 200 c.c. beaker placed inside a Dewar flask over an insulating material ; 50 c.c. of water at about 33° were taken in the beaker. Anhydrous sodium sulphate (30 g.) was added to the water in the beaker. The mouth of the Dewar flask was closed by means of a cover of asbestos sheet, provided with three bores, one for passing a mechanical stirrer driven by a motor and another for introducing a Beckmann thermometer. The solution was allowed to cool and as soon as the mercury thread passed the point corresponding to the transition point between the decahydrate and the anhydrous sodium sulphate, some quantity of Glauber's salt ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was added to the beaker by the third opening. After a little recalescence phenomenon, the mercury thread began to rise. A stop-watch was started at this point. After 20 minutes (usually) the temperature was found to be constant. It gives the transition point of sodium sulphate in water. The tracing of the cooling curve during the determination of the transition point is found to be unnecessary as it is observed that the temperature attained at the twentieth minute gives the transition temperature accurately.

The maximum recalescence observed by the author is 0.5° even by introducing Glauber's salt as a seeding material and the maximum recorded by others is 1.9°.

It has been reported by Bye (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1942, 9, 517) that the conversion of 50 g. of water into the solid phase of the hydrated sodium sulphate takes 10 hours. So the amount of water taken up by the anhydrous sulphate to transform into hydrated salt during 20 minutes is small.

The molecular lowering of the transition point can be determined with the help of the formula,

$$K = \frac{M}{m} \times \Delta t \times \frac{50 + V}{100} \quad \dots (A)$$

where Δt = observed lowering of the transition point,

K = molecular constant for 100 g. of the solvent,

M = molecular weight of the substance,

m = wt. of the substance taken,

V = volume in c.c. of the added solution.

In the present work 50 c.c. of 0.1M sodium pyrophosphate solution were taken in the beaker. The temperature of the solution was raised by heating to near about 34°. Anhydrous sodium sulphate (30 g.) was added to it. The beaker was then placed inside the Dewar flask and the mouth of the Dewar was closed by the cover. The Beckmann thermometer was introduced into the solution and the mixture was rotated by means of a

stirrer. Now the calculated amount of beryllium sulphate solution was added to the solution in the beaker so that the ratio of pyro : beryllium = 2 : 1. The transition point of the sodium sulphate was determined as already stated. The temperature was noted. The difference between the two readings, that is when only water is taken and the present gives the observed lowering in the transition point Δt . The value of the constant K is found out with the help of the equation (A). Comparing the experimental value with that of the theoretical, the molecular form of the complex ion of the type $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-6}$ is determined.

Quantity of salt used.	Conc. of pyro/conc. of Be	Δt .	K_f
5.25 c.c. of 0.4772M BeSO_4 soln.	2 : 1	0.1	11.05

The experimentally observed value of the cryoscopy constant is nearly half the value of the molecular constant for single ion (18.2). That is, the number of ions (other than sodium sulphate) present in solution is nearly half the number of pyrophosphate ions used. If it be so, then the complex ion of the type pyro : beryllium = 2 : 1 exists in simple monomeric form as $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-6}$. The slightly higher value of the observed constant from that of the theoretical value is explained as due to the existence of equilibrium of the type :

in solution.

Thus in a solution containing excess of pyrophosphate ion and beryllium ion, the complex ions $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2]^{-6}$ and $[\text{Be}(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)]^{-2}$ exist as follows :

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